

Acoustic parameters by ultrasonic interferometric measurements of substituted Schiff's bases

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Abstract : In last four decades ultrasonic velocity and density measurement studies created its own importance in medicinal, pharmaceutical, anatomical, biochemical and chemical sciences¹⁻⁴. As solute-solvent, solute-solute, solvent-solvent, solute, solvent and metal ion interactions were studied by this techniques, the drug effects, drug actions and drug activity as well as drug absorption were studied by this technique. Hence, taking all these things into consideration, an ultrasonic velocity and density measurements of ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_1), 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_2), 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-nitrophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_3) and 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-chlorophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_4) were carried out in ethanol and dioxane solvents. To investigate solute-solvent, solute-solute interactions at 307.15 K. Adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k), intermolecular free length (L_f), relative association (R_A), specific acoustic impedance (Z), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) were determined. The effects of various substituents on ligands and solvents on interactions were investigated for drug activity, action and effect of Schiff bases.

Keywords : Schiff's bases, solute-solvent interactions, interferometric study, acoustic parameters.

Introduction

Ultrasonic velocity and densities of 3-(2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole (L_1), 1-phenyl-3-(2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylphenyl)-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)pyrazoline (L_2) in dioxane and different percentage of dioxane-water mixtures at different temperatures (303, 308, 313, 323 K) have been evaluated at 0.01 M concentration⁴. Different acoustic properties like partial molal volume (ϕ_v), adiabatic compressibility (β_s), apparent molal compressibility ($\phi_{k(s)}$), intermolecular free length (L_f), relative association (R_A) and specific acoustic impedance (Z) have been determined by using single crystal interferometer at 1 MHz frequency. The obtained results have been interpreted in terms of solute-solvent interactions. Ultrasonic parameters are being extensively used to study molecular interaction in pure liquids⁵⁻⁷, liquid mixtures⁸⁻¹⁰ and electrolytic solution¹¹. A presentation in terms of the measured parameters such as velocity of ultrasonic waves, through indicative of existence of an interaction does not provide any interaction about it.

The use of ultrasound was proved to be useful probe for generating more information on many areas and review articles on various topics such as organometallic chemistry¹, biochemistry², polymerisation³, medical use and in conjugation with other fields have been published by Mills¹², Algeria¹³ and Toys¹⁴. A fast and highly efficient method for the synthesis of some of the Schiff bases of aminothiazolylbromocoumarin (**4a-m**) has been performed by microwave irradiation of 2'-amino-4'-(6-bromo-3-coumarinyl)thiazole (**3**) and substituted aromatic aldehydes (**a-m**). Microwave assisted reactions have resulted in better yields of the desired products than when prepared under conventional conditions. The resulting products were evaluated for their qualitative and quantitative antibacterial activity¹⁵. Ultrasonic waves have acquired the status of an important probe for the study of structure and properties of matter¹⁶.

Ultrasonic velocity and density measurement of 2-hydroxy-3-substituted-5-methyl- α -bromoacetophenones and 2-(4'-*H*/chloro)-benzylidene-5-methyl-7-substituted

coumarane-3-ones were carried out in ethanol and dioxane respectively for solute-solvent, solute-solute interactions. These interactions were also performed with Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} metal ions at 303.15 K. The data obtained during the study is used for determining the most significant acoustic parameters like apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) and specific acoustic impedance (Z). These parameters explore solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions in different solvents¹⁷.

The ultrasonic velocity of vanadium laurate confirms that there is a significant interaction between the solute-solvent molecules in dilute solution and the carboxylate molecules do not aggregate appreciable in dilute solutions. The value of Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) for vanadium laurate is in agreement with those obtained from other physical parameters. The effects of concentration and chain length of soap on ultrasonic velocity and the various acoustic parameters (apparent volume, adiabatic compressibility, apparent molal compressibility, intermolecular free length, relative association, specific acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity compressibility and relative association solvation number) have been investigated¹⁸. Nikam and Hasan¹⁹ have studied temperature and concentration dependence of ultrasonic velocity and allied parameter of monochloroacetic acid in aqueous ethanol. Ultrasonic study of binary liquid mixtures of *m*-xylene with 1-alkanol at 303.15 K was done by Prabhavati *et al.*²⁰. Ultrasonic velocity in 1,3-dioxane-water mixture has been measured by Baumgartner and Atkinson²¹. Ultrasonic velocity of water-dioxane solutions of tetracycline hydrochloride and chlorotetracycline at 298.15 K and 308.15 K are measured by Pandey²². Deshmukh²³ studied ultrasonic behaviour of substituted acrylophenone and its complexes with Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Cr^{II} in acetone as a solvent and different acoustic properties such as apparent molar volume, apparent molar compressibility, intermolecular free length etc. have been determined. Raghuwanshi^{24,25} studied various acoustic parameters of benzopyrazoline and its complexes with Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cr^{II} and Fe^{II} in 70% dioxane-water mixture. Literature survey shows that much work has been done in water and organic solvent mixtures, but scanty work is found in pure ethanol and dioxane solvent and comparison of interactions in these different solvents.

Taking all these things into consideration, we intended

to analyze comparative study of these ligands in ethanol and dioxane solvents to investigate protic-aprotic nature, polarity-nonpolarity, hydrogen bonding, dielectric constant and density of solvent on solute-solvent, ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. Hence, in this present investigation attempt is made to understand behaviour of substituted Schiff's bases viz. 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_1), 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_2), 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-nitrophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_3) and 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-chlorophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_4) compounds in ethanol and dioxane solvents separately with respect to V , d , β_s , ϕ_k , ϕ_v , L_f , R_A and Z .

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. (i) 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_1), (ii) 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-1-(α -*o*-methylphenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_2), (iii) 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-nitrophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_3), (iv) 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-1-(α -*p*-chlorophenylimino)ethyl benzene (L_4) were synthesized as described in literature²⁶. Munot²⁶ deals only with the synthesis and characterization of various Schiff's bases of 2-hydroxy-3-substituted-5-chloro-1-(α -substituted phenylimino)ethyl benzene.

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|------------|----------------------|-----------------------|
| (1) R = H | R' = CH ₃ | R'' = H |
| (2) R = Br | R' = CH ₃ | R'' = H |
| (3) R = H | R' = H | R'' = NO ₂ |
| (4) R = H | R' = H | R'' = Cl |

1,4-Dioxane and ethanol were purified by described method²⁷. Densities were measured with the help of bicapillary pycnometer, 0.001 M solution of ligand in ethanol and dioxane solvents were prepared separately, weighing was made on Mechaniki Zaktady Precynnyej Gdansk balance made in Poland (± 0.001 g). A special thermostatic arrangement was done for density and ultrasonic velocity measurements. Elite thermostatic water bath

was used, in which continuous stirring of water was carried out with the help of electric stirrer and temperature variation was maintained within ± 0.1 °C. Single crystal interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, Model MX-3) with accuracy of $\pm 0.03\%$ and frequency 1 MHz was used in the present work. The densities and ultrasonic velocity of ligands in ethanol solvent were measured at 307.15 K. Similar measurements were carried out in case of dioxane solvent also.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation, measurements of densities and ultrasonic velocities of L_1 to L_4 in dioxane and ethanol had been carried out and given in Tables 1 and 2.

Ultrasonic velocity (V) :

Ultrasonic velocity of L_1 to L_4 when investigated in dioxane and ethanol solvents, it was observed that the ultrasonic velocities in dioxane medium are higher than the alcohol medium. It was also noted that (Figs. 1, 2 and Tables 1, 2) when the concentration of ligand at 0.01, 0.005, 0.0025 and 0.00125 in dioxane solvent, then the trend was

$$L_4 > L_1 > L_3 > L_2$$

while in ethanol it was found to be

$$L_1 > L_4 > L_2 > L_3$$

Velocity of L_1 ligand is higher than other, this observation is same for all concentrations. The change in the

Table 1. Acoustic parameters for ligands in dioxane at 307.15 K (Freq. = 1 MHz)

Ligand	Conc. (mol dm ⁻³)	ν (m s ⁻¹)	d (kg m ⁻³)	$\beta \times 10^{-6}$ (pa ⁻¹)	ϕ_k (m ³ mol ⁻¹ pa ⁻¹)	$\phi_v \times 10^3$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	R_A	L_f (Å)	Z (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
L_1	0.01	595.35	1.0278	2.7	-0.1353	-3.6720	0.9826	1.0450	611.9008
	0.005	527.33	1.0212	3.5	-0.1043	-6.2110	1.0165	1.1898	538.5128
	0.0025	503.42	1.0134	3.8	-0.0765	-9.4477	1.0245	1.2398	510.1680
	0.00125	496.71	1.0128	4.0	0.0065	-18.6590	1.0285	1.2720	503.0690
L_2	0.01	457.20	1.0290	4.6	0.0562	-3.7222	1.0742	1.3641	470.4588
	0.005	427.95	1.0280	5.3	0.2526	-7.5618	1.0971	1.4642	439.9326
	0.0025	405.82	1.0269	5.9	0.7461	-14.9888	1.1155	1.5448	416.7388
	0.00125	402.69	1.0254	6.0	1.5731	-29.0448	1.1167	1.5579	412.9192
L_3	0.01	601.20	1.0135	2.7	-0.1277	-2.1496	0.9657	1.0450	609.3162
	0.005	438.80	1.0117	5.1	0.2215	-4.2163	1.0707	1.4363	443.9340
	0.0025	429.33	1.0092	5.3	0.5234	-7.6985	1.0758	1.4642	433.2832
	0.00125	419.51	1.0030	5.6	1.2937	-10.6639	1.0775	1.5050	420.7696
L_4	0.01	660.17	1.0144	2.2	-0.1780	-2.2526	0.9369	0.9433	669.6779
	0.005	558.71	1.0127	3.1	-0.1761	-4.4318	0.9888	1.1198	565.8067
	0.0025	547.42	1.0113	3.2	-0.3107	-8.5665	0.9942	1.1377	553.6081
	0.00125	542.45	1.0080	3.3	-0.5310	-14.7188	0.9940	1.1553	546.7896

Table 2. Acoustic parameters for ligands in ethanol at 307.15 K (Freq. = 1 MHz)

Ligand	Conc. (mol dm ⁻³)	ν (m s ⁻¹)	d (kg m ⁻³)	$\beta \times 10^{-6}$ (pa ⁻¹)	ϕ_k (m ³ mol ⁻¹ pa ⁻¹)	$\phi_v \times 10^3$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	R_A	L_f (Å)	Z (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
L_1	0.01	362.32	0.9714	7.8	-0.0862	-1.8698	1.0127	1.7762	351.9576
	0.005	385.82	0.9694	6.9	-0.3280	-3.6296	0.9896	1.6706	374.0160
	0.0025	409.24	0.9670	6.1	-0.9271	-6.6268	0.9680	1.5708	395.7393
	0.00125	417.55	0.9666	5.9	-1.9916	-13.2228	0.9611	1.5448	403.6091
L_2	0.01	339.82	0.9696	8.9	0.0123	-1.6183	1.0326	1.8974	329.4916
	0.005	355.60	0.9680	8.1	-0.1154	-3.2850	1.0154	1.8101	344.2208
	0.0025	387.00	0.9675	6.9	-0.6410	-6.7323	0.9870	1.6706	374.4225
	0.00125	392.34	0.9654	6.7	-1.4253	-12.2452	0.9801	1.6462	378.7677

Table-2 (contd.)

L ₃	0.01	296.36	0.9698	11.7	0.2567	-1.6867	1.0810	2.1754	287.4134
	0.005	337.60	0.9680	9.0	0.0411	-3.3346	1.0332	1.9080	326.7968
	0.0025	365.42	0.9656	7.7	-0.3650	-6.0716	1.0038	1.7648	352.8517
	0.00125	383.90	0.9636	7.0	-1.2036	-10.9551	0.9854	1.6827	369.9260
L ₄	0.01	343.91	0.9690	8.7	-0.0052	-1.6221	1.0279	1.8759	333.2498
	0.005	347.51	0.9676	8.5	-0.0455	-3.2704	1.0228	1.8542	336.2517
	0.0025	353.73	0.9648	8.2	-0.1886	-5.7842	1.0139	1.8212	341.2819
	0.00125	435.77	0.9598	5.4	-2.2802	-8.1538	0.9409	1.4780	418.2534

Fig. 1. Ultrasonic velocity of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

Fig. 2. Ultrasonic velocity of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

velocities is due to the fact that at low concentration all the alcohol molecules are separate and forms dipole. In dioxane medium L₄ ligand have higher ultrasonic velocity because of presence of two chlorine atoms. Cl atoms have more nucleophilic character as compared to Br.

Density (d) :

Density is also one of the important property. Density value in dioxane medium is considerably higher than in alcohol medium, this may be due to nature of medium.

L-Dioxane > L-Ethanol

In case of dioxane and ethanol, from Tables 1, 2 and Figs. 3, 4 following comparison of ligand can be done on the basis of different concentrations for ligands L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄ the concentration like 0.01, 0.005, 0.0025 and 0.00125.

In dioxane density of L₂ is greater than other.

$$L_2 > L_1 > L_4 > L_3$$

In ethanol density of L₁ is higher than other.

$$L_1 > L_2 > L_3 > L_4$$

This observation is same for all concentrations i.e. 0.01, 0.005, 0.0025 and 0.00125.

Adiabatic compressibility (β) :

Adiabatic compressibility can be evaluated by using Laplace's equation,

$$\beta = 1/V^2.d$$

β values in dioxane medium are considerably smaller than in ethanol medium. This may be due to nature of solvents. The parameters of solvents, which directly affect the values of β, are aprotic nature, non-polarity, low di-

Fig. 3. Density of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

Fig. 4. Density of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

electric constant and higher density of dioxane as compared with protic nature, polarity, high dielectric con-

stant and lower density of ethanol. In ethanol, hydrogen bonding is possible while it is not observed in dioxane.

From Tables 1 and 2, β values for all ligands in alcohol solvent are higher than those in dioxane.

L-Dioxane < L-Ethanol

From Fig. 5, in dioxane L₂ has greater β values than L₃, L₁ and L₄ but in ethanol L₃ ligand have higher value of adiabatic compressibility than L₂ and L₂ have higher value than L₄ and L₁ (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5. Adiabatic compressibility of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

From Figs. 5 and 6 it is clear that in ethanol L₃ ligand have higher β value and in dioxane L₂ ligand have higher β value, this may be due to the presence of nitro, chloro and bromo group in the structure. -I effect of Cl are acting in the ligand, so these ligands (L₃ and L₂) have highest dipole moment. -NO₂ group have -I and -R effects; the -R effect is the predominant effect²⁸.

Apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) :

Molar compressibility (ϕ_k) is another important acoustic parameter. Thus, the structure of solute and the number of atoms present in it will have direct effect on ϕ_k values.

L-Dioxane > L-Ethanol

The ϕ_k values for the ligands in ethanol solutions are lower than those in dioxane solution.

An addition of polar solute having a partial positive

Fig. 6. Adiabatic compressibility of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

Fig. 8. Apparent molar compressibility of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

Fig. 7. Apparent molar compressibility of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

charge on hydrogen atom, there is every possibility that there can be a weak interaction between this positive charge and negative charge on oxygen atom (due to electronegativity) of dioxane.

From Tables 1 and 2, in case of dioxane the ϕ_k value for ligand L₁ and L₄ is negative while for L₂ and L₃ it is positive. In case of ethanol almost all ligands show negative values for ϕ_k . The positive values of ϕ_k shows that electrostatic force in the vicinity of ion causes solvation of solute. It is well known that solute causing electrostriction leads to decrease in compressibility of solution which is reflected by negative value of ϕ_k .

Apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) :

ϕ_v is the thermodynamic property of solutions, which express the solute-solvent interactions.

Tables 1 and 2 shows that the ϕ_v values are increasing whereas,

$$L\text{-Dioxane} < L\text{-Ethanol}$$

Ethanol medium have higher ϕ_v value than dioxane medium.

In dioxane medium the L₃ ligand have highest ϕ_v value (Fig. 9).

$$L_3 > L_4 > L_1 > L_2$$

This comparison taken on the basis of different concentrations i.e. 0.01, 0.005, 0.0025 and 0.00125.

In dioxane and ethanol solvent negative ϕ_v values obtained (Tables 1 and 2) indicate compactness of medium

Fig. 9. Apparent molar volume of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

and after dissolution of solute due to closer packing of molecules inside the shell more clinging is occurring.

ϕ_v values for L₃ in dioxane and ethanol (Figs. 9 and 10) are the highest among the ligands. In this ligand presence of -NO₂ group having -I and -R effect; the -R effect

Fig. 10. Apparent molar volume of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

is predominant effect²⁸.

Relative association (R_A) :

R_A is an acoustic property of understanding interaction, which is influenced²⁹ by two opposing factors :

(i) breaking of solvent structure on addition of solute to it and

(ii) solvation of the solutes that are simultaneously present by the free solvent molecules.

The former effect results in the decrease in R_A values while the latter resulting in increase of R_A values.

From the Tables 1, 2 and Figs. 11, 12, it can be easily seen that the R_A values in dioxane are higher than in alcohol for the ligands, which is a reverse trend than that is observed for β . The general trend can be shown as :

L-Dioxane > L-Ethanol

The alcohol molecules are well known to be associated as compared to dioxane, which are not associated due to hydrogen bonding. As soon as solute is added to alcohol as well as dioxane, the probability of solute forming association with alcohol will be lesser as compared to dioxane. This is evident because the existing association in alcohol will render less probability of alcohol forming association with solute than dioxane. This is actually observed in case of relative association as shown in Figs. 11 and 12.

Fig. 11. Relative association of L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄.

Fig. 12. Relative association of L_1 , L_2 , L_3 and L_4 .

Intermolecular free length (L_f) :

L_f is one of the important acoustic properties to study the intermolecular interactions.

As evident from Table 1 and Fig. 13, L_f value get decreased because dioxane is a non-polar solvent having

Fig. 13. Intermolecular free length of L_1 , L_2 , L_3 and L_4 .

higher density and no hydrogen bonding. Therefore, already packing of dioxane molecules occurs in the structure and hence it become less compressible. When a polar solute is added it also get associated in the structure by electrostriction thus decreasing the free space available. Therefore, in ethanol the L_f values are higher but as the size of solute increases the L_f values slightly decreases as clearly indicated by inspection of Table 2 and Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Intermolecular free length of L_1 , L_2 , L_3 and L_4 .

In case of dioxane, because of its non-polar nature the compact packing of molecules is already there and when polar solute is added because of its association again free space decreases. Therefore, the L_f values in dioxane must be smaller.

Specific acoustic impedance (Z) :

Specific acoustic impedance also makes the contribution in explaining molecular interactions. The mathematical relation for specific acoustic impedance $Z = \nu \cdot d$ and adiabatic compressibility $\beta = 1/\nu^2 \cdot d$ shows that their behaviour is opposite. Specific acoustic impedance is the complex ratio of the effective sound pressure at a point to the effective particle velocity at that point³⁰.

It can be seen from Fig. 15, that the values of Z are continuously decreasing on changing the structures of

Fig. 15. Specific acoustic impedance of L_1 , L_2 , L_3 and L_4 .

ligands (L_1 to L_4) and in dioxane solvents the values are much higher than in ethanol solvent (Tables 1 and 2). This can happen only when the effective particle velocity increases; this in turn means that dispersion forces should be active in mixture, a result anticipated in the absence of any specific interactions such as hydrogen bonding³¹ etc. On the contrary, the Z values in ethanol are lower indicating hydrogen bonding.

Further in Figs. 15 and 16 between Z and ligands show the reverseness in trends that is the values for alcohol are lower than dioxane. The variations in Z values are,

$$L\text{-Dioxane} > L\text{-Ethanol}$$

Thus, the specific acoustic impedance depends upon the various structures of the liquid and the molecular packing in the medium.

Measurement of ultrasonic velocity is the best tool to investigate solute-solvent, solute-solute and ion-solvent interactions. Therefore, in last four decades ultrasonic interferometric study created its own identity for determining solute-solvent interactions. By this study, β , ϕ_k , L_f , R_A , Z etc. acoustic properties are determined which explain how these interactions occur and responsible for breaking and making of the structure in the solution. So

Fig. 16. Specific acoustic impedance of L_1 , L_2 , L_3 and L_4 .

in the present work these acoustic parameters were studied for already synthesized ligands, which are used as solutes.

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